

BRIDGING THE GAP: UTILIZATION OF INTERACTIVE GAMES THROUGH CLASSPOINT APPLICATION TO INCREASE PUPILS' PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS 4 SYNCHRONOUS LEARNING

Francris C. Basijan

Juan Sumulong Elementary School, Antipolo City/Rizal, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

With learners growing more digitally aware by the day, it is necessary to develop more relevant ways to the use of technology in the classroom. This research determined the effectiveness of the Utilization of Interactive Games Through ClassPoint Application in enhancing the mathematics performance of grade 4 learners. This study used a pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design. The study's participants were grade 4 students from Juan Sumulong Elementary School S.Y. 2021-2022. Among the grade 4 learners, 25 pairs were selected using match-pairing. These pairs of learners were from the online distance learning modality and modular learning distance modality. The mean and standard deviation were used to assess participants' performance in pretest and post-test. Likewise, an independent t-test was used to evaluate the significant difference between the two groups' pretest and posttest. This study was able to determine that the use of interactive games using the ClassPoint Application in teaching Mathematics can assist learners improve their performance. It was concluded that the planned intervention met the needs of the learners' numeracy challenges.

Keywords: *interactive games, ClassPoint application, innovation, learning outcomes*

INTRODUCTION

The use of technology in instruction has become essential in the ever-changing field of education in order to provide interesting and successful teaching strategies. The issue for educators is to adapt traditional teaching methodologies to a digital environment as the globe moves towards online distant learning. The teaching of mathematics is one field that has undergone significant change, and the use of interactive games via platforms such as ClassPoint is a potent tool in this endeavor.

The typical classroom environment frequently depends on chalkboards and textbooks, limiting the opportunities for dynamic and immersive learning experiences, particularly in a topic as dynamic as mathematics. However, with the introduction of online platforms such as ClassPoint, educators now have a diverse tool at their disposal to take mathematics instruction to new heights.

Interactive games can help students have a better understanding of mathematical ideas. Educators may convert seemingly complicated mathematical problems into interesting challenges that captivate students' attention and create a love of learning by introducing gamification aspects into classes. ClassPoint's interactive capabilities make it possible to seamlessly integrate these activities into virtual classrooms, bridging the gap between traditional and online teaching approaches.

The use of interactive games in mathematics education not only provides a fun factor, but it also develops students' critical thinking skills and problem-solving ability. Educators may use ClassPoint to build interactive quizzes, puzzles, and simulations that stimulate active involvement and make learning more interesting and effective. This strategy not only accommodates different learning styles, but also guarantees that students are actively engaged in their own learning path.

Furthermore, through the integration of ClassPoint with interactive games, instructors may track and analyze student progress in real time. This useful feedback loop allows teachers to discover areas of difficulty, modify their teaching tactics, and give personalized help to individual pupils. The platform's data analytics capabilities enable instructors to make more informed decisions, resulting in better student results.

In accordance with its legislative mandate, DepEd has released directives on flexible learning and resources, particularly DepEd Order No. 021, s. 2019, in addition to the K–12 Basic Education Program Policy Guidelines. It describes FLOs, or Flexible Learning Options. FLO, remote learning, and alternative delivery modes have been used throughout this epidemic and must be embraced in order to ensure students' safety and the continuation of their education. Self-Learning Modules (SLM) based on DepEd's most important learning skills (MELCS) are used in modular learning, a sort of online learning. As part of blended learning, students get instruction via a range of media, such as the internet, television, radio, and printed materials.

Even though some parents have voiced anxiety over their children's future education. Despite the outbreak, the Department of Education has declared that other methods would be used dependent on pupils' access to technology and their condition. "Some of the classes will be delivered through various platforms, while others will be completed at home," said Education Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones at a virtual press conference. Educational institutions are working hard to discover solutions to this tough problem.

On the other hand, the worldwide pandemic provides a chance for educators to improve the way they teach students in any topic utilizing several media. It may be a problem for many, but on the bright side, it would be an opportunity to improve one's abilities and tactics in the teaching and learning process. The current scenario, on the other hand, is unfamiliar to everyone; no official training or preparation was provided for the execution of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the continuation of education in the new normal, and it has become a hot subject among educators, parents, and students. Nonetheless, everyone must confront the problems posed by the public health crisis, and as Secretary Leonor Briones of the Department of Education stated, "Time is of the essence, and teachers, students, and parents must learn to adapt."

Juan Sumulong Elementary School polled students before the start of the School Year 2021-2022 to choose their favorite learning modality throughout the pandemic. A poll found that modular learning is the most requested learning delivery method among students for their children this school year. However, most Grade 4 parents preferred Distance Blended instruction (a blend of modular and online instruction).

As a result, Juan Sumulong Elementary School addressed and catered to students who selected blended learning. Using synchronous online distance learning is a difficult mode of delivery because teaching online without meeting my students directly is very difficult and difficult to decide or select on what particular teaching strategy will suit my learners' needs, interests, and abilities and can guarantee maximum retention and application of the learning that is achieved.

Because modular learning is designed for independent learning during offline learning, no teachers must provide ongoing encouragement and assistance to students when learning becomes tough, stressful, dull, or uninteresting. The majority of students and parents complained about what and how to accomplish the assigned chores, and teachers also complained about decreased pupil learning achievement. As a result, the author, as the Grade 4 GT adviser, began conceptualizing a support teaching method that will cognitively boost the learners and target kids who may struggle in learning Mathematics using a blended learning modality.

Quality teaching should not be neglected in the advancement of education. According to study of Rondina and Roble (2019) mathematical game-based design activities such as "A Line To Win" was an effective method to improve computational skills of the students while the "Slide A Picture" was instrumental in teaching the students the sketching of the graphs of a quadratic functions. Furthermore, the mathematics game-based design activities demonstrated a positive influence on students learning gains in Algebra. With

this, teachers in mathematics may integrate game-based design activities in teaching to make the learners enjoy and arouse their interest in the process of learning and they hope that this way of learning may continue in the future in their upper-level mathematics. Since this study focused only on two offline mathematics game-based design activities, teachers may also explore other games such as those digitally based activities where adventure, simulation and strategy are integrated and provides students with animations and further analyze the impact on these strategy on students' attitude and study habits. In depth analysis may also be considered on student-to-student interaction during the implementation of game-based activities as well as their level of creativity in solving mathematical problems.

White (2019) revealed that there is a strong relationship between game-based learning and student attitude and achievement in mathematics, there are important limitations to note. The study was limited in the areas of size, duration, and content. The results from the study represent the findings from one sample of students during one week of the year, focused on one unit of the curriculum. In order to gain more significant insight into the effects of GBL on student attitude and achievement and to control for potential extraneous variables, more research should be conducted.

The results of this study have many implications for teachers and students in the math classroom. The participants demonstrated significant improvements both in their attitudes about math and their achievement in ordered pairs. Thus, this action research study corroborated the literature surrounding the positive impact of serious games on attitude and achievement. These results may encourage other researchers and practitioners to continue investigating. The teacher researcher author will definitely continue investigating and integrating game-based learning into instruction on a regular basis.

According to the study of Ramli et al (2020), state that the application of technology in the teaching and learning process is in line with the needs of nowadays' students. The application of GBL with the help of technology has a great impact in helping to improve the quality of teaching and learning of Mathematics. The application of GBL has a positive impact on student motivation and involvement in Mathematics learning. Further reading should be made on the motivational impact of student self-efficacy. This is because previous studies have also found that student motivation influences students' self-efficacy in that students who believe in their own abilities are more motivated to engage in learning (Bandura, 2006). This indicates that low levels of student motivation result in lower student self-efficacy in Mathematics. Therefore, the application of GBL in Mathematics needs to be explored in order to impact the quality of teaching and learning of Mathematics.

Gaylo et al (2019) revealed that the mathematical aptitude of the respondents was at Low Average, showing that the learners showed little knowledge and understanding in the mathematical concepts tested. Moreover, the extent of exposure of the learners in the study is Slightly Exposed to the different levels of interactive games. Further, there is no significant difference in the mathematical aptitude of secondary school learners when

grouped according to the levels of interactivity of games they play and their extent of exposure.

In the study of Sapin and Orbon (2022) state that using game-based learning the students' capacity to think were developed, comprehend underlying ideas, and solve challenging mathematical problems when they learn mathematics through games. While having fun, educational games encourage students to come up with original ideas and push them to learn more quickly. Instructional games only make arithmetic ideas easier for pupils to comprehend and retain. Their confidence is increased by the conversations students have with one another to provide a lasting learning effect. Together, games help learners feel powerful and on par with their peers. Moreover, game-based learning using different game application tools emphasizes the importance of strengthening the foundation of math concepts and the mathematical proficiency to solve various problems in math.

According to the study of Khalid et al (2022), the results show that digital GBL helped increase the students' achievement in mathematics. Moreover, the LA process could be used as a mathematics achievement prediction model. In this regard, data on login frequency, duration of use, and the score to predict could be used to predict the intervention's impact on mathematics achievements. The study concludes by discussing the findings and their implications towards GBL and LA-based research and practice in mathematics teaching and learning. The application of game-based learning (GBL) provides many benefits, such as helping to improve the quality of the mathematics teaching and learning process.

To ensure that teachers provide quality and appropriate instruction for the various types of learners when it comes to teaching mathematics, this study presents an innovation that addresses the needs of the learners while also motivating them to learn Mathematics even through distance learning. The research's major goal is to make the teaching-learning process more interactive. Using ClassPoint to teach Mathematics will make the subject more attractive to the students. Furthermore, the objective of the study is to determine the use of engaging and interactive games through ClassPoint application in increase the performance and boost pupils' involvement in Mathematics 4.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of the utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as support strategy during pandemic and identify pupils learning' experiences after the intervention. Specifically, the researcher seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of learning performance of the two groups of respondents exposed and unexposed to interactive games through ClassPoint application as revealed in the pretest and posttest results?
2. Is there a significant difference on the level of learning performance of the two groups of respondents exposed and unexposed to interactive games through ClassPoint application as revealed in the pretest and posttest results?

3. What action plan may be proposed to enhance the Mathematics Performance of Grade 4 pupils?

METHODOLOGY

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The respondents of this study were the grade 4 learners of Juan Sumulong Elementary School, District II-A, City Schools Division Office of Antipolo, School Year 2021-2022. They were selected through using the match-pairing technique. A match-pairing strategy was applied in this study. This method is frequently used to place one individual in a treatment group and the other in a comparison group. Before the study, two groups of grade 4 students were given the pre-test. The learners who partnered with their match based on their results were the study's participants after the scores were analyzed. The experimental group consisted of 25 learners who received blended-distance delivery learning, whereas the unexposed group consisted of 25 learners who received modular-distance learning.

Table 1. Participants of the Study

Group	N	Selected Participants	Blind Participants
Exposed Group	40	25	15
Unexposed Group	40	25	15
Total	80	50	30

Table 1 shows the outcomes of the study's participant selection process. It appears that there were only 50 learners out of 80 participants, with 25 pairings selected by match-pairing. According to the pretest findings, 30 learners were classified as blind participants who did not have a pair.

The utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application was employed as one of the key instruments in this study, and survey questionnaires will be used to validate the Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application prior to its deployment. It includes questions that focus on the MELCs as well as entertaining activities to help pupils learn math.

The researcher's pretest and posttest were utilized as instruments in measuring the efficacy of the use of Interactive Games via ClassPoint Application. The pretest and posttest comprised twenty questions covering the same learning abilities. It covered the MELCs that were addressed over the week.

Participants' performance in the pretest and posttest was calculated using the mean and standard deviation. Similarly, to establish the significance of the difference in pretest and posttest scores between the two groups, an independent t-test was used.

Furthermore, the dependent t-test (or paired sample t-test) was utilized in this study. The dependent t-test compares the means of two groups that are closely connected to see if there is a statistically significant difference.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The researcher submitted the research proposal for examination and approval to the Schools Division Office-Research Evaluation Committee. Following approval, the letter of consent/assent was delivered to the parents to determine whether they would allow their children to participate in the study. The questionnaire was floated or emailed by messenger link. The assessment pretest was given to students with parent aid or supervision before the intervention, and the post-test was administered after the intervention. The questionnaires were disinfected both before and after distribution. The responses were categorized using an appropriate coding system, and the data was tabulated for better presentation.

RESULTS

Table 2

Level of Learning Performance of the Two Groups of Respondents Exposed and Unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as Revealed in their Pretest and Posttest Results

%	Verbal Interpretation	Exposed				Unexposed			
		Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
90% - 100%	Highly Proficient	0	0	12	48	0	0	0	0
75% - 89%	Proficient	0	0	13	52	0	0	5	20
50% - 74%	Nearly Proficient	7	28	0	0	7	28	20	80
25% - 49%	Low Proficient	18	72	0	0	18	72	0	0
0% - 24%	Non-Proficient	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total		25	100	25	100	25	100	25	100
Highest Score		10		20		10		15	
Lowest Score		5		15		5		10	
Mean		7.8		17.48		7.76		12.68	
Mean Percentage Score		39		87.4		38.8		63.4	

Std. Deviation	1.85	2.14	1.89	1.88
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Table 3

Result of the t-test in the Significant Difference on the Level of Learning Performance of the Two Groups of Respondents as Revealed in the Pretest and Posttest Results

Group	Test	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Ho	VI
Exposed	Pretest	40	7.8	1.85	17.1097	0.000	Rejected	Significant
	Posttest	40	17.48	2.14				
Unexposed	Pretest	40	7.76	1.89	9.2280	0.000	Rejected	Significant
	Posttest	40	12.68	1.88				

DISCUSSION

1. Level of Learning Performance of the Two Groups of Respondents Exposed and Unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as Revealed in their Pretest and Posttest Results

Table 2 presents the level of learning performance of the two groups of respondents exposed and unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as revealed in their pretest and posttest results.

As depicted on the table, pupils who utilized interactive games through ClassPoint application obtained 18 or 72 percent in the pretest interpreted as Low Proficient and 13 or 52 percent in the posttest interpreted as Proficient. Meanwhile, pupils unexposed to interactive games obtained 18 or 72 percent in the pretest interpreted as Low Proficient and 20 or 80 percent in the posttest interpreted as Nearly Proficient.

The table depicts that the learning performance of the pupils exposed to the utilization of interactive games through ClassPoint Application obtained a mean of 7.8 in the pretest and 17.48 in the posttest and a standard deviation of 1.85 and 2.14, respectively. On the other hand, pupils who are unexposed to innovation obtained a mean of 7.76 in the pretest and 12.68 in the posttest and a standard deviation of 1.89 and 1.88, respectively.

It can be noted that pupils in the exposed group obtained the mean percentage score of 39 in the pretest and 87.4 in the posttest. Hence, the unexposed group obtained 38.8 mean percentage score in the pretest while 63.4 were obtained in the posttest.

This means that the exposed groups of pupils obtained a proficient performance as reflected from their average scores as reflected in the posttest. This further means that majority of the pupils exposed to the innovation have a Proficient performance.

2. Significant Difference on the Level of Learning Performance of the Two Groups of Respondents Exposed and Unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as Revealed in the Pretest and Posttest Results

Table 3 presents the result of the t-test on the significant difference on the level of learning performance of the two groups of respondents exposed and unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as revealed in the pretest and posttest results.

As gleaned from the table, the computed t-values on the learning performance of the respondents exposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application with a computed t-values of 17.1097 obtained probability values of 000 lesser than .05 level of significance. On the other hand, pupils who are unexposed to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application obtained computed values of 9.2280 with probability values of .000 lesser than .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypotheses for the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application are rejected and found significant. This further explains that on the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application both groups improved to a certain level as revealed in the pretest and posttest result, thus, it is significant.

The study concluded that pupil-respondents improved their learning performance before and after exposure to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application as revealed on the results of the pretest and posttest. This means that exposure to the Utilization of Interactive Games through ClassPoint Application may improve the learning performance of pupils in Mathematics subjects.

This implies that exposure to different programs of learning enhances the quality of teaching and learning. This also provides pupils to acquire certain knowledge and skills to a certain subject during exposure to a certain program.

Conclusions

Based on the data collected and analyzed, the null hypotheses, which state that there is no significant difference between the formative tests, posttest, and pretest mean scores of the two groups, were rejected. Moreover, the results show that the utilization of Interactive Games Through ClassPoint Application in teaching mathematics can help strengthen the performance of the learners. It may also be inferred that students enjoy technology-based learning activities. It follows that the intervention's design was successful in meeting the needs of the students' numeracy problems.

Recommendations

Using the findings and conclusions as bases, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. The teachers are encouraged to conduct numeracy programs and activities to enhance the level of learning performance of grade four pupils.
2. The school management must support the teachers' efforts. Financial assistance should also be acknowledged.
3. Teachers may receive technical support from school and department heads in the development and validation of materials. The conduct of various programs and activities with regards to mathematics may be deemed helpful to the improvement of pupils learning performance. 4. Further studies may conduct studies along this area using other variables.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Some ethical considerations that researchers must be mindful of, especially during the process of gathering and presenting research data: The rights to privacy of the individuals involved. The nature of participation in the research must be voluntary and the individuals involved must have the right to withdraw partially or completely from the process. All participants must provide their consent first. Maintenance of the confidentiality of data provided by individuals as well as identifiable participants' anonymity. How participants react to the researchers' methods in seeking to collect data. How the participants will be affected by the way in which data is analyzed and reported. The behavior and objectivity of the researcher.

This research was guided by the ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality and showed no harm to participants. Under some reasonable grounds, the specific characteristics and answers of the respondents was held confidential. To secure the informed consent of the respondents or participants in this study, the questionnaires open with a letter described the purpose of the study. The respondents were instructed that they were free not to participate in the study and answer the survey instrument, they were assured that their schools' identities would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

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REFERENCES

- DepEd Order No. 021 s. 2019. Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program. From <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/08/22/august-22-2019-do-021-s-2019-policy-guidelines-on-the-k-to-12-basic-education-program/>
- Gaylo, D., et al., (2019) Interactive Online and Offline Games: Their Influence to The Mathematical Aptitude Of Secondary School Learners. From https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333828669_Interactive_Online_And_Offline_Games_Their_Influence_To_The_Mathematical_Aptitude_Of_Secondary_School_Learners
- Khalid, F. et al (2022) Digital Game-based Learning and Learning Analytics in Mathematics. Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction, Vol. 13, No. 1, 2022 (pp. 168-176).
- Orbon and Sapin (2022) Effectiveness of Game-Based Learning Instructional Materials in Enhancing the Mathematics Performance of Grade 8 Learners. From https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370816763_Effectiveness_of_Game-Based_Learning_Instructional_Materials_in_Enhancing_the_Mathematics_Performance_of_Grade_8_Learners
- Ramli I. et al (2020) Game-Based Learning and Student Motivation in Mathematics. International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development, 9(2), 449–455.
- Rondina, Janneth Q., Roble, Dennis B., (2019) Game-Based Design Mathematics Activities and Students' Learning Gains. From: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/596837>
- White K. et al (2019) Effects of Game-Based Learning on Attitude and Achievement in Elementary Mathematics. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1206814.pdf>

